

I-CARE (CONNECT, ADAPT, RESPONSE, EMPATHIZE) PERCEIVED STRESS LEVEL MONITORING SYSTEM: ITS EFFICIENCY AND APPLICABILITY TO ASSESS TEACHERS AS BASIS FOR STRESS INTERVENTION PROGRAM

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 32

Issue 9

Pages: 1102-1106

Document ID: 2025PEMJ3124

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14947083

Manuscript Accepted: 02-10-2025

I-Care (Connect, Adapt, Response, Empathize) Perceived Stress Level Monitoring System: Its Efficiency and Applicability to Assess Teachers as Basis for Stress Intervention Program

Vicente B. Labadia Jr.* Marissa D. Uy, Martin I. Diaz
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study entitled i-CARE (Connect, Adapt, Response, Empathize) PERCEIVED STRESS LEVEL MONITORING SYSTEM: ITS EFFICIENCY AND APPLICABILITY TO ASSESS TEACHERS AS BASIS FOR ADMINISTRATION STRESS INTERVENTION PROGRAM with a problem, 1. 1. What is the level of Applicability& Efficiency of the devised i-CARE v2 Stress Perceived Level Monitoring System?, 2. What is the level of confidentiality with regards to teachers' data privacy and security, and, 3. What is the suitability level of device for Administration in addressing timeliness, and efficiency of the data, thereby providing the necessary immediate intervention, thereby providing the necessary immediate intervention. It was conducted in Tacurong National High School with 64 Senior High School teachers with loads/subjects in SY 2024-2025, and administrator. Both were given surveys. The result was very good in all aspects. In the light of the findings and conclusion it is hereby recommended that devised be uniformly used in all DepEd Schools for a more efficient results and Perceived stress level databank. The device will also be used in a wider scope and in other schools.

Keywords: *I-Care, stress level, stress intervention program*

Introduction

Teachers are important contributors to society. They pass on knowledge, foster critical thinking skills, inspire students and parents, serve as role models, and play a role in the holistic development of children. Teachers are also promoters of peace, motivators for pursuing dreams, and builders of communities, thereby influencing society positively (Bryan, 2024).

In the Philippines, teachers in the public school system always work extra miles to better provide their services to the students (Baluyos, et al., 2019). They usually handle an extensive workload which consists of too many clerical tasks, working beyond school hours to help in school programs or to conduct remedial lessons to his/her students, not to mention working on other varied tasks until the wee hours at night to prepare their lessons for the next day (Harmsen et al., 2018). Their tasks are not limited to teaching alone but also with other community programs that overlap with their time outside of schools, reducing their time for the family and even their rest (Simbre et al., 2021).

The high workload demands of teachers are also said to be contributory to the country's Learning Poverty Index. Given this, Philippine education officials should focus on the safety and health of Filipino teachers by addressing their stress and burnout issues. Several findings of this study give support to the literature on teacher burnout and working conditions. Specifically, results showed that on average, each teacher works 12.17 hours a day, handles five classes, and teaches 141 students. These contribute to very high stress and high emotional exhaustion, moderate depersonalization, and moderate personal accomplishment. It was revealed that factors of gender, educational attainment, educational stage of teaching, type of school, province, work setup, age, and years in teaching interplay with stress and burnout (Cammayo et al., 2022).

On the other hand, DepEd Secretary Sonny Angara issued DepEd Order No. 12, Series of 2024, amending DepEd Order No. 010, Series of 2024, which outlines the Policy Guidelines on implementing the revised K to 10 Curriculum, also known as the "MATATAG Curriculum." It added that Schools shall ensure fair and equitable distribution of teaching loads while protecting the overall welfare of teachers (Malipot, 2024).

A scenario that emphasizes the stress as major problem, was an incident that took last September 2024 where in Teacher in Tibagon Elementary School loss her life due to this certainty (Leal, 2024).

With this, the researchers created a study named "i-CARE V.2 Applicability and Efficiency to assess Teachers Stress Perceived Level: Basis for Stress Intervention program." This study aims to answer the following questions: 1.) What is the level of acceptability& Efficiency of the devised i-CARE v2 Stress Perceived Level Monitoring System?2.) What is the level of confidentiality with regards to teachers' data privacy and security? and 3.) What is the suitability level of device for Administration in addressing timeliness, and efficiency of the data, thereby providing the necessary immediate intervention?

Research Questions

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of Applicability& Efficiency of the devised i-CARE v2 Stress Perceived Level Monitoring System?
2. What is the level of confidentiality with regards to teachers' data privacy and security?
3. What is the suitability level of device for Administration in addressing timeliness, and efficiency of the data, thereby

- providing the necessary immediate intervention?
4. Based on the result, what mechanism and process framework can be developed to maximize the utilization of the i-CARE V2 Perceived Stress Monitoring System?

Literature Review

According to Gokalp (2008) that as stress level increased likelihood of using effective strategies decreased, and likelihood of using ineffective strategies increased. Results also showed that having more experience and more behavior management training did not necessarily lead to more effective strategy selection.

According to Lee, E. (2022) confidentiality important in building trust, promotes confidence (in the healthcare system, in the school system, in the workplace etcetera), prevents misuse of confidential information (illegal or immoral use), protects reputation, Employment may depend on it (e.g. non-disclosure agreement) and it ensures compliance with the law.

According to Glosoff & Pate (2002) the concepts of privacy and confidentiality are integrally related, especially in regard to the counseling relationship, privacy being broader in nature. Beauchamp and Childress (2001), in a widely acknowledged work on biomedical ethics, noted the importance of allowing those clients professionals to help to limit and control access to information about themselves. They defined privacy as allowing individuals to limit access to information about themselves while defining confidentiality as allowing individuals to control access to information they have shared.

According to Atiase, Bamber & Tse (1989) that after controlling for firm size, the length of the reporting delay is inversely related to the magnitude of report period price revaluations. That is, longer delays are associated with smaller market reactions, when firm size is held constant. There is some evidence that this relation may be stronger for earnings announcements which convey “bad news.”

Innovation, Invention, and Strategy

The i-CARE V2 PERCEIVED STRESS LEVEL MONITORING SYSTEM is an innovation that connects to the internet where users can access anywhere. It is an online platform that addresses stress problems encountered in school through various features. The system has an intelligent capability to interpret teachers through Evaluation Form. The app sends an immediate and quick evaluation so that the administrator/school could see the result in a single click.

In terms of negative emotions, teachers critically control experiences and occasionally completely conceal it. (Hagenauer & Volet, 2014)

Traditional evaluation takes time, and in these unpredictable situations, they may only notice problems too late. The system quickly gives data of the problems encountered and their reasons, and with this, administrators can make a possible intervention.

Methodology

Respondents

The study is conducted at Tacurong National High School-Senior High School. The respondents of the study are Senior High School teachers that have load/subjects on Grade 11 and Grade 12 or both.

Instrument

There are two (2) sets of research instruments which were used in the study. These are the research questionnaire utilized in finding out the Applicability and efficiency, confidentiality and Suitability as perceived by the validators, users and administrator.

Time duration of conducting the research took one hundred twenty (120) hours or 3 months of validating and testing the devised system.

The judgment and analysis of the data were done by the 1 Master Teacher teaching/working with ICT (Information and Communication Technology) and two (2) ICT Experts within the City Schools Division of Tacurong.

Evaluation and validation of instrument were answered by the panel of ICT experts and evaluators. They had evaluated the devised system using a validated rubric.

For the evaluation of the panel of experts, the Likert- five(5) scale below was used.

After evaluation, the panel of experts gave another page for their comments and suggestions for the improvement of the study.

To analyze and interpret the data, this study used Mean gain score to determine the efficacy, applicability, confidentiality and suitability of the developed i-CARE V2 Perceived Stress Level Monitoring System.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 implies that the system is excellent and very capable of capturing Perceived Stress Evaluation Form and teacher’s evaluation result are securely stored in the database which is only accessible for administrator which promotes confidentiality on the side of

teachers and administrator engagement.

Table 1. *System applicability and efficiency as perceived by Teachers and Administrator*

No.	Indicator	Teacher	Administrator
1	The system displays Perceived Stress Level evaluation.	4.54	5
2	The system displays information of my profile.	4.67	5
3	The system displays the evaluation test whenever I want it.	4.54	
4	The system allows login of accounts.	4.75	5
5	The online platform's option is easy to click.	4.75	4
6	The control in the online platform is easy to recognize through the use of friendly images and icons.	4.71	5
7	The system does not require paper and pencil in taking the evaluation.	4.71	5
8	I can use the system anytime and anywhere.	4.67	5
9	The questions are easy to understand.	4.54	4
Grand Mean		4.65	4.75

According to Lee, E. (2022) confidentiality important in building trust, promotes confidence (in the healthcare system, in the school system, in the workplace etcetera), prevents misuse of confidential information (illegal or immoral use), protecting reputation, Employment may depend on it (e.g. non-disclosure agreement) and it ensures compliance with the law.

Table 2. *Level of confidentiality with regards to teachers' data privacy and security*

<i>Level of Confidentiality with regards to students' data privacy and security</i>		
No.	Indicator	Teachers
1	The system allows me to answer the Perceived Stress Level without interference/influence of other people.	4.67
2	Other teachers don't know what my answers in the evaluation form are.	4.75
3	The system motivates me to express my feelings through answering the evaluation form.	4.54
Grand Mean		4.65

Table 2 implies that in terms of Level of confidentiality with regards to teachers' data privacy and security of device for teachers to address perceived stress entity in the system is excellent in allowing teachers to take the perceived stress evaluation without interference/influence, confidentiality of answers, and motivating to express their feeling to engage with the system.

Generally, the statement is supported by Glosoff & Pate(2002) the concepts of privacy and confidentiality are integrally related, especially in regard to the counseling relationship, privacy being broader in nature. Beauchamp and Childress (2001), in a widely acknowledged work on biomedical ethics, noted the importance of allowing those clients professionals to help to limit and control access to information about themselves. They defined privacy as allowing individuals to limit access to information about themselves while defining confidentiality as allowing individuals to control access to information they have shared.

It was also supported by A Gokalp (2008) that as stress level increased likelihood of using effective strategies decreased, and likelihood of using ineffective strategies increased. Results also showed that having more experience and more behavior management training did not necessarily lead to more effective strategy selection.

Table 3. *Suitability level of device for Administrator in addressing timeliness and efficient data providing the necessary immediate intervention*

<i>Suitability level of the devised i-CARE V2 PERCEIVED STRESS LEVEL MONITORING SYSTEM</i>		
No.	Indicator	Administrator
1	The system sends me perceived stress level evaluation of teachers which serves as basis for action taken.	5
2	The system helps me get in track of teacher's stress endeavor.	5
Grand Mean		5

Table 3 implies that in terms of Suitability level of device for Administrator in addressing timeliness and efficient data providing the necessary immediate intervention the system is excellent in sending perceived stress level evaluation of teachers and very good in helping to send teacher's stress endeavor.

It was supported by Atiase, Bamber & Tse(1989) that after controlling for firm size, the length of the reporting delay is inversely related to the magnitude of report period price revaluations. That is, longer delays are associated with smaller market reactions, when firm size is held constant. There is some evidence that this relation may be stronger for earnings announcements which convey "bad news."

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the I-CARE V2 PERCEIVED STRESS LEVEL MONITORING SYSTEM has the standard of very good in terms of applicability, efficiency, and immediate Perceived stress response. In totality, it has featured that suits accessibility and applicability of software for teachers and administrators.

In the light of the findings and conclusion of the research study, the following are hereby recommended:

The devised I-CARE V2 PERCEIVED STRESS LEVEL MONITORING SYSTEM should be uniformly used in all DepEd Schools for more efficient results and online Perceived stress level databank.

Other types of validated questionnaires should be added to the system, to address other concern dimensions of teacher's progress.

There should be a centralized department that should attend to this concern, especially in large schools.

References

ATIASE,K., BAMBER,L., & TSE,S.(1989). Timeliness of financial reporting, the firm size effect, and stock price reactions to annual earnings announcements. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1911-3846.1989.tb00722.x>.

Baluyos,R., Rivera,H., & Baluyos,E(2019). Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Work Performance. <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation?paperid=94433>.

Byan,(2024). 12 Reasons Why Teachers Play A Crucial Role In Society. <https://www.teachersoftomorrow.org/blog/insights/reasons-why-teachers-play-a-crucial-role-in-society/>. (Retrieved September 24, 2024)

Cammayo,P.,Aquino,C.,& Gomez, M.G.(2022). Factors Predicting Stress and Burnout of Filipino Teachers Engaged in Remote Learning. <https://journals.upd.edu.ph/index.php/pjlir/article/view/9397>.

Farasat and Nikolaev (2016). Social structure optimization in team formation. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0305054816300983>

Fawcett and Cooper(2001). Process integration for competitive success: Benchmarking barriers and bridges. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/eum000000006385/full/html>.(Retrieved September 24, 2024)

Franks,T.(1999). Capacity building and institutional development: reflections on water. [https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-162X\(199902\)19:1%3C51::AID-PAD54%3E3.0.CO;2-N](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/(SICI)1099-162X(199902)19:1%3C51::AID-PAD54%3E3.0.CO;2-N). Danish,

Glosoff,L., & Pate,R.(2002). Privacy and Confidentiality in School Counseling. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/H-Glosoff/publication/234700799_Privacy_and_Confidentiality_in_School_Counseling/links/0f31753c545050206f000000/

Gokalp,G.(2008). Effects of stress on teacher decision making. <https://www.proquest.com/docview/304462330?fromopenview=true&fromunauthdoc=true&pq-origsite=gscholar&>

Leal,G.B.(2024). DepEd to probe teacher's death in Davao de Oro allegedly due to stress from principal. <https://news.tv5.com.ph/local/read/deped-to-probe-teachers-death-in-davao-de-oro-allegedly-due-to-stress-from-principal>.

Lee, E. (2021).What is Confidentiality?. <https://cpdonline.co.uk/knowledge-base/safeguarding/what-is-confidentiality/#:~:text=>

Malipot,M.(2024). DepEd revises MATATAG Curriculum implementation, emphasizes teacher welfare protection. <https://mb.com.ph/2024/9/18/dep-ed-revises-matatag-curriculum-implementation-emphasizes-teacher-welfare-protection>

Ramzan, and Ahmad(2013). Effect of Perceived Organizational Support and Work Environment on Organizational Commitment; Mediating Role of Self-Monitoring. https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/78399112/Effect_of_Perceived_Organizational_Suppo20220108-27645-cok8au

Simbrel,A.,Palad,I., & Salazar,C.(2021). How Protected are Teachers and School Personnel?: Critical Analysis of The Teacher Protection Act (Senate Bill 956). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/359202523_How_Protected_are_Teachers_and_School_Personnel_Critical_Analysis_of_The_Teacher_Protection_Act_Senate_Bill_956.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Vicente B. Labadia Jr.

Tacurong National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Marissa D. Uy

Tacurong National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Martin I. Diaz

Tacurong National High School
Department of Education – Philippines